

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF BIOCHAR ON SOIL N, P, K CONTENT, PH, ENZYME ACTIVITY AND SOIL WATER HOLDING CAPACITY

Shukurov O.,

*Faculty of Biology of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek,
Tashkent Uzbekistan*

*Institute of Fundamental and Applied research of the "TIAME" National Research University,
Tashkent Uzbekistan*

Egamberdieva D.,

Faculty of Biology of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent Uzbekistan

*Institute of Fundamental and Applied research of the "TIAME" National Research University,
Tashkent Uzbekistan*

Jabbarov Z.

Faculty of Biology of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent Uzbekistan

*Institute of Fundamental and Applied research of the "TIAME" National Research University,
Tashkent Uzbekistan*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436609>

Abstract

In this study, the effect of biochar samples prepared on the basis of chicken manure and household waste on the amount of macro-elements, pH values, the activity of enzymes, and total moisture holding capacity of soybean-planted soils were studied. It was determined that biochar samples have a positive effect on the general condition of the soil.

Keywords: biochar, soil, macro-elements, enzymes, pH, moisture holding capacity.

Introduction

Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (NPK) levels in soil are constantly changing and generally decreasing because of feeding of them plant and soil-dwelling microorganisms, while nitrogen is also rapidly changing and decreasing as a result of leaching and volatilization [1]. Therefore, chemical fertilizers are used in different proportions according to the type of soil, the amount in the soil and the plant's demand in each vegetation period [2]. However, the use of chemical fertilizers negatively affects soil quality over time. In such cases, it is advisable to use environmentally friendly and effective organic fertilizers. For example, applying biochar made from various organic wastes to soil increases soil fertility and improves its physical condition [3].

In recent years, the application of biochar to soil has attracted the attention of the scientific community. A lot of researches focused on aspects such as its cost-effectiveness, environmentally friendly properties, and remediation of contaminated soil. Biochar can affect soil nutrients in several ways: as a nutrient source for plants and soil microorganisms; as a nutrient receiver; affects the mobility of nutrients; changes soil properties [4,5]. Therefore, the purpose of this research work was to study the effect of biochar on soil N, P, K content, enzyme activity and soil water retention capacity.

Materials and methods

An experiment was conducted using biochar samples on the soils of our research area, and the changes in the agrochemical, physical and biological properties of the soils were studied in laboratory conditions.

The soil pH were determined according to the N. I. Alamovsky method. The organic carbon was determined by burning in a thermostat at 150-160 °C for 20 min [6]. Total nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were determined in one soil sample by the Mesheryakov method, nitrogen and phosphorus were determined by the photoelectrocolorimeters method, and potassium was determined by a flame photometer [7]. The amount of nitrates was determined by the disulfophenol method [8]. Full field moisture capacity was determined using the laboratory method of I.O. Kabaev [9]. The effect of biochar on the activity of 3 types of enzymes in soils was determined. Catalase enzyme activity was determined by P.S. Kasnelsona and V.V. Ershova method, invertase enzyme activity by Khaziev.F.X method, urease enzyme activity by I.I. Romeyko and S.M. Malinsky method [10].

Results and discussion

In the studies, changes of NPK amount in the soil with the use of biochar without the use of mineral fertilizers and the planting of leguminous crops were determined. According to the results, the amounts of nitrogen in biochar applied soybean fields were 23.58mg/kg, 25.41mg/kg, and 21.52. mg/kg when using household waste biochar, chicken manure biochar, and control samples respectively (Table 1).

Phosphorus contents were 32.56, mg/kg 34.52 mg/kg and 31.51 mg/kg in household waste-biochar, chicken manure-biochar applied soil and control samples. In this case, the amount of phosphorus increased by 0.95 mg/kg in the option where chicken manure-biochar was used, which is explained by the fact that the

phosphorus in chicken manure is stored in the biochar, while in the other options, the amount of phosphorus decreased, that is, this result can be explained by the assimilation by plants (Table 1).

The mobile amount of potassium element also changed differently, for example, it was 238.41 mg/kg

in the control, 242.21 mg/kg in the case of household waste-biochar, and 240.12 mg/kg in the case of chicken manure-biochar. It can be seen that an increase in potassium content was observed when using biochar, this increase due to the potassium content of biochar is explained by the creation of favorable conditions for plant nutrition and its absorption (Table 1).

Table 1

The effect of biochar on the amount of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium elements in the soil, mg/kg

Experience options	The amounts of elements		
	Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potassium
Control	21,52	31,51	238,41
Household waste-biochar	23,58	32,56	242,21
Chicken manure-biochar	25,41	34,52	240,12

According to the researches, 2 positive scientific results were obtained as a result of the use of biochar, firstly, leguminous crops, as a result of the use of biochar, an increase in the amount of potassium in the soil was achieved, the creation of favorable conditions for their assimilation and their assimilation by plants is a positive result, because the higher assimilation of nutrients in the soil by plants is also very important, and the

growth and development of plants and their productivity depend on it.

In the experiments, the effect of biochar on the change of soil pH was studied. According to the results, the soil pH was neutral in the control, and in the experimental options, the pH was decreased even the environment did not change (Table 2).

Table 2

The effect of biochar on soil pH

Experience options	Soil samples
Control	7,32
Household waste-biochar	6,85
Chicken manure-biochar	6,61

According to the data in the table, the pH values were 6.85, 7.16, and 7.32 in the soil samples treated with household waste-biochar, chicken manure-biochar, and in the control accordingly.

The effect of biochar on the activity of catalase, invertase and urease enzymes in the soil was studied. According to the results, catalase enzyme activities were 3.00 ml O₂/g soil, 15.50 ml O₂/g soil, and 8.33 ml O₂/g soil in the control, the household waste-biochar applied soil samples, chicken manure-biochar applied soil samples respectively. In the general analysis of catalase enzyme activity showed the highest result in soybean planted and the household waste-biochar applied soil samples. According to the results, invertase enzyme activities were 2.92 mg glucose /g soil, 3.25 mg

glucose /g soil, and 3.08 mg glucose /g soil in the control; household waste-biochar, chicken manure-biochar applied soil samples. Urease enzyme activity also had different activity in different soil variants. In control samples urease enzyme activity was 4.59 mg NH₃/g soil, in household waste biochar applied soil samples was 6.85 mg NH₃/g soil and in chicken manure-biochar applied soil samples was 5.78 mg NH₃/g. The results of the study show that the activity of urease enzyme has changed according to the type of biochar. The highest result was found in the household waste biochar applied soil samples, which was explained by the increase in the amount of microorganisms in the soil and the improvement of their activity (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The effects of biochar samples on soil enzymes activities in soil samples collected from biochar applied soybean fields.

The high water retention capacity of the biochar to the soil is considered another physical property. Therefore, in this work we studied the impact of biochar on water holding capacity of the soil. In the experiments, typical irrigated gray soils were taken and samples of biochar from chicken manure, and household waste

were applied at 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 3% and the effect on the total moisture capacity of the soil were determined. According to the results, it was found that, the type of biochar production raw material play a major role in having the highest soil moisture capacity (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The effect of biochar samples on total moisture capacity of soil, %

In the studies, when chicken manure-biochar was used, the highest soil moisture content was 50.14% in the variant with 2% of biochar. In the household waste-biochar sample, the highest soil moisture content was 53.63% at the 3 % op biochar, which was 11.17% higher than the control.

In conclusion, biochar samples improved the amounts of macro-elements, soil enzymes activities, moisture capacity and decreased pH values compared with control samples. The biochar samples obtained from chicken manure was effectiveness compared with biochar prepared from household wastes.

References:

1. Tim J. Clough, Leo M. Condon, Claudia Kammann, Christoph Müller A Review of Biochar and Soil Nitrogen Dynamics. *Agronomy* 2013, 3, 275-293; doi:10.3390/agronomy3020275
2. Rojmul Hussain, K.Ravi, Ankit Garg Influence of biochar on the soil water retention characteristics (SWRC): Potential application in geotechnical engineering structures. *Soil and Tillage Research* Volume 204, October 2020, 104713 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2020.104713>
3. Houssou Assa Albert, Xiang Li, Paramsothy Jeyakumar, Lan Wei, Lianxi Huang, Qing Huang, Muhammad Kamran, Sabry M.Shaheen, Deyi Hou, Jörg

Rinklebe, Zhongzhen Liu, Hailong Wang Influence of biochar and soil properties on soil and plant tissue concentrations of Cd and Pb: A meta-analysis. *Science of The Total Environment* Volume 755, Part 2, 10 February 2021, 142582 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142582>

4. Pokharel Prem, Ma Zilong, Chang Scott X. Biochar increases soil microbial biomass with changes in extra- and intracellular enzyme activities: a global meta-analysis. *Biochar* volume 2, pages65–79(2020)

5. Wang Jianlong, Wang Shizong Preparation, modification and environmental application of biochar: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* Volume 227, 1 August 2019, Pages 1002-1022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.282>

6. Аринушкина. Е.В Руководство по химическому анализу почв. М. МГУ.1970. – 488 с.

7. Определение подвижных форм фосфора и обменного калия в почвах (методы Кирсанова, Чирикова, Мачигина).

8. Грандваль-Ляжу Определение нитратов по методу ЦИНАО, 1984, с.158-159.

9. А.А.Корчагин М.А.Мазиров Н.И.Шушкевич Физика Почв Лабораторный Практикум 2011 й.

10. Хазиев.Ф.Х Методк почвенной энзимологии 2005 й 252 с.